

Evaluation Of Diuretic Potency And Anti-Urolithiatic Efficacy of Ethanolic Root Extract of *Solanum Indicum* Linn.; An In Vivo And In Vitro Approach

***Karthika D P, Gayatri Panicker**

¹Department of Pharmacology, Mount Zion College of Pharmaceutical Sciences and Research, Chayalode P.O, Adoor, Pathanamthitta District, Kerala, India

²Department of Pharmacology, St. Joseph's College of Pharmacy, Cherthala, Kerala, India

ABSTRACT

The present study examined the effects of *Solanum indicum* Linn. root on diuretic in experimental rats and in vitro anti-urolithiatic activity. By using ethanol as the solvent, the plant extract was prepared from the shade-dried root. The extract was then subjected to a preliminary phytochemical analysis. The preliminary phytochemical investigation revealed the presence of alkaloids, glycosides, flavonoids, tannins, phenolic compounds, and sterols in the ethanolic root extract of *Solanum indicum* Linn. Acute toxicity study as per OECD guideline 423 was performed and ethanolic root extract was nontoxic up to dose 2000 mg/kg body weight. The diuretic activity was evaluated by Lipschitz method at two different doses of ethanolic root extract (200 and 400mg/kg). Parameters like urine volume, diuretic index, Lipschitz value and urine electrolyte concentration of sodium, potassium and chloride was evaluated. In accordance with Lipschitz values, the plant had 63% and 87% diuretic efficacy when compared to furosemide at the low dose and high dose of crude extract respectively. The present study clearly indicated that the ethanolic root extract of *Solanum indicum* Linn. showed higher calcium oxalate crystallization inhibition (56.6 %) for the titrimetric method.

Keywords: Diuretics, Anti-urolithiatics, Urolithiasis, *Solanum indicum* Linn., Furosemide, Cystone

INTRODUCTION

A chemical that accelerates the production of urine is known as a diuretic. Diuretics generally function by increasing the output of urine along with sodium excretion from the body through the urine. Most diuretics work primarily by preventing sodium from being transported at one or more of the four major anatomical points along the nephron where sodium reabsorption occurs. Depending on whether it increases renal excretion of sodium, chloride, sodium chloride, potassium, bicarbonate, or calcium, a diuretic typically possesses a combination of natriuretic, chloruretic, saluretic, kaliuretic, bicarbonaturetic, and calciuretic properties. [1] Diuretics are used for edematous conditions that cause an excess of fluid in the body, such as heart failure, cirrhosis, and nephritic syndrome. Diuretics are used in therapeutic strategies to control fluid overload that manifests as ankle swelling, ascites, and/or

pulmonary edema. They help balance fluid and help shift fluid out of the interstitium, which results in significant symptomatic relief and improved health-related quality of life for patients.[2] Diuretics such as the high-ceiling loop and thiazides diuretic have been associated with several side effects, such as electrolyte and metabolic changes, new-onset diabetes development, renin-angiotensin system activation and weakening of sexual function. This fact necessitates that there is a strong need for novel diuretics which are relatively safe with better or equivalent diuretic activity.[3]

Urolithiasis is the development of urinary calculi (stones), which can occur anywhere in the urinary system. It includes nephrolithiasis (formation of kidney stones), ureterolithiasis (formation of stones in the ureters), and cystolithiasis (formation of bladder stones), but calculus often arises in the kidney. In patients undergoing post-operative therapy for renal

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and ureteric calculi, recurrent stone development is likely the most significant issue.^[4] Urolithiasis can be developed from diet, urinary tract infections, changed urine solutes and colloids, decreased urinary drainage and urinary stasis, prolonged immobilization, Randall's plaque, microliths, and other factors.^[5] There isn't a synthetic medication that adequately treats urolithiasis at the moment. Surgical methods, diuretics, analgesics, urine alkalinization, and in certain circumstances, allopurinol therapy are available as treatment options. Numerous herbal remedies have been shown to have beneficial effects against urolithiasis, and these remedies have been found to have less toxicity and adverse effects than other treatments.^[6]

Studies have shown that most of the herbs with anti-urolithiatic activity exhibit a pronounced diuretic property. The contribution of diuresis to the anti-urolithiatic property of these herbs can be explained by their ability to increase the urinary rate and volume (diuresis) which facilitates the removal of small crystals and reduce the chance of these crystals from growing or aggregating. Diuretics have been introduced and widely been accepted as anti-urolithiatic agents. For example, thiazides, a potent group of diuretics, which have effectively been used for the treatment of hypercalciuric nephrolithiasis and prevention of renal calcific stone reported to produce a significant increase in urinary oxalate excretion during long-term therapy in patients with calcium oxalate nephrolithiasis.^[7]

Solanum indicum Linn. commonly known as 'Brihati' in Sanskrit, is used in Ayurveda system of medicine either as a single drug or in combination with other drugs. In the form of decoction (1in10) half a teacupful twice daily is given in dysuria. It is a much-branched perennial under shrub with prickle. The plant grows mostly in warmer parts of the country up to an altitude of 1500 m. ^[8] According to Ayurvedic systems of medicine, this plant is beneficial in a variety of conditions. The root of the plant is commonly used in the event of dysuria and incontinence. The roots are also beneficial in the treatment of odontalgia, dyspepsia, flatulence, colic, verminosis, diarrhea, leprosy, strangury, cough, asthma, fever, skin diseases, respiratory and cardiac disorders, ulcers, and poisonous affections, among other

things.^[8] Various class of phytoconstituents such as steroidal saponins, steroidal glycosides, sesquiterpenoids, hydroxycoumarins, phenolic compounds, coumarins, coumarinolignoid alkaloids, saponin, fatty acid, glycerides of the oil, polysaccharides, triterpenes were reported from different part of plant.^[9] *Solanum indicum Linn.* is used in the Ayurveda system as a diuretic, but the effect of this drug is not experimentally proven on animals. Therefore this study aims to evaluate its diuretic potential along with its anti-urolithiatic efficacy using in vivo, in vitro and in silico approaches.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Collection, identification and preparation of ethanolic root extract

The root of *Solanum indicum Linn.* was collected in the month of September 2022 from Sahachara Herbals, Kollam district, Kerala and was authenticated by Dr. Sreeja Krishnan, Assistant Professor, Post Graduate Department of Botany, Sree Narayana College, Cherthala, Kerala. The collected roots of approximately 2 kilograms of *Solanum indicum Linn.* were washed thoroughly with water to remove soil particles, shade dried and powdered coarsely with a mechanical grinder and stored in an air tight container. The powder (500g) was defatted using petroleum ether then extracted by Soxhlet extraction using ethanol as solvent. The extract was filtered through Whatmann filter paper to remove impurities if any present and dried by BOD incubator at 45°C. The crude extract was placed in air tight container and stored in refrigerator at 40°C until used in the screening.^[10]

Preliminary phytochemical screening

The ethanolic extract of *Solanum indicum Linn.* was subjected to qualitative analysis to investigate the presence of various phytochemical constituents such as carbohydrates, glycosides, phytosterols, proteins, phenols, tannins and flavonoids.

Experimental animals

Healthy Wistar albino rats (150-250g) were procured from College of Veterinary and Animal Sciences,

Mannuthy P.O, Thrissur, Kerala-680651 (Reg.No.:328/GO/ReBt-S/Re-L/01/CPCSEA, 10/03/22). All animals were kept in polypropylene cages and reared at animal house of St. Joseph's College of Pharmacy, Cherthala (Reg. No.: 1405/PO/Re/S/11/CPCSEA) in a conducive environmental condition i.e., temperature ($22\pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$), humidity ($45\pm 5^{\circ}\text{C}$) and 12-hour dark and light cycle. Animals were fed ad libitum with normal laboratory chow standard pellet diet. All the studies were conducted in accordance to the guidelines approved by the Institutional Animal Ethics Committee St. Joseph's College of Pharmacy, Cherthala.

Acute toxicity studies

Acute toxicity studies were performed for the ethanolic *Solanum indicum* Linn. root extract as per limit test of OECD guideline 423. 6 healthy young adult non - pregnant female rats (150-200g) were randomly selected, marked and kept in the cage five days prior to dosing. Animals were fasted prior to dosing; food was withheld with adequate supply of water. After the fasting period, the animal was weighed and test substance was administered. The dose (2000mg/kg) was prepared prior to administration. Test substance was administered as single dose by oral gavage in fraction not exceeding 24 hours. Food was withheld for 3-4 hours after test substance administration. After dosing animals were observed for 30 minutes and special attention given for first four hours and daily thereafter, for a total of 14 days.

Screening of diuretic activity

Lipschitz test is employed for the assessment of the diuretic activity of ethanolic root extract of *Solanum indicum* Linn. The animals should be fasted for 18 h prior to experiment allowing only water during the fasting period. Healthy Albino Wistar rats are selected and divided into four groups consisting of six rats in each group. Group I: Normal control group; receives 0.5% sodium carboxymethyl cellulose orally at the dose of 10 ml/kg. Group II: Standard group: receives furosemide orally at the dose of 10 mg/kg. Group III and Group IV serves as test groups and receives the ethanolic root extract orally at a low dose and at a high dose respectively. Immediately after administration of respective treatments, the animals are kept in

metabolic cages individually for the collection of urine. The urine will be collected for 5 h after the dose was administered. The bladder is emptied by pulling the base of the tail of each rat. Diuretic assay parameters such as total urine volume, diuretic index, Lipschitz value and amount of urine electrolytes like sodium, potassium and chloride were estimated. Estimation of Na^+ and K^+ content of the urine samples treated with the root extract at different doses as well as other groups is done by direct ISE method. The urinary Na^+ and K^+ content of the respective test groups were also compared with that of control and standard group. ^[11]

Diuretic index = Mean urine volume of the test group / Mean urine volume of the control group

Lipschitz value = Mean urine volume of the test group / Mean urine volume of the reference group

Evaluation for anti-urolithiatic activity

Step1: Preparation of experimental kidney stones (calcium oxalate stones) by homogenous precipitation

1.34gm of sodium oxalate was dissolved in 100 ml of 2N H_2SO_4 and 1.47gm of calcium chloride dihydrate was dissolved in 100ml distilled water. Both were mixed equally in a beaker to precipitate out calcium oxalate. The precipitate freed from traces of H_2SO_4 by ammonia solution. Washed the precipitates with distilled water and dried at 60°C for 4 hours.

Step -2: Estimation of calcium oxalate by Titrimetry

The dissolution percentage of calcium oxalate was calculated by taking exactly 1 mg of calcium oxalate and 10mg of different plant extracts, packed it together in a semi permeable membrane. This was allowed to suspend in a conical flask containing 100ml of 0.1M Tris buffer. Then 1 mg of calcium oxalate in semi permeable membrane acts as the control. The 1 mg of calcium oxalate and 10 mg of Cystone (standard) and 10mg of and ethanolic plant extracts in semi permeable membrane. All conical flasks containing semi permeable membrane was kept in an incubator to 37°C for 2hours. Remove the contents of semi permeable membrane in to separate

test tube, add 2ml of 1N sulphuric acid to each test tube and titrated with 0.9494N KMnO₄ till a light pink color end point obtained. The amount of remaining undissolved calcium oxalate is subtracted from the total quantity used in the experiment in the beginning to know the total quantity of dissolved calcium oxalate by various extracts. Each ml of 0.9494 N KMnO₄ is equivalent to 0.1898mg of Calcium oxalate.

The percentage dissolution calculated follows,

Dissolved calcium oxalate = (Total quantity used in the Experiment in the beginning) - (Undissolved calcium oxalate)

Percentage dissolution = $\frac{\text{Dissolved calcium oxalate}}{100} \times 100$

Statistical analysis

Results were expressed as Mean \pm Standard Error of Mean, $p < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant. Data obtained was analyzed by one-way ANOVA using Graph pad prism version 7.

RESULTS

Preliminary phytochemical screening

The ethanolic root extract revealed the presence of carbohydrates, glycosides, alkaloids, flavonoids,

steroids and phenolic compounds. Numerous chemicals, including flavonoids, saponins, and organic acids, have been shown in studies to be potentially responsible for the diuretic effects of plants [12]. According to studies, the diuretic properties of flavonoids may result from their interaction with adenosine A1 receptors [13]. Some studies have also shown that diuretic activity might be due to the consequence of alkaloids [14]. The exact site, molecule, and cellular mechanisms have not yet been fully understood.

Acute toxicity studies

Animals were observed for behavioral signs of toxicity like motor activity, tremor, etc., and no significant toxic signs were observed during 14 days. The results of the acute toxicological studies revealed that the administration of ethanolic extract of *Solanum indicum L.* by oral route up to 2000mg/kg body weight did not produce any mortality and it was tolerated.

Volume of urine

Oral administration of the ethanolic *Solanum indicum L.* root extract increased the urinary flow in a dose-dependent manner ($p < 0.001$) as shown in table 1. When compared with control, high dose is approximately 3 times and low dose 2 times more potent in urine excretion.

Table 1: Effect of *Solanum indicum* Linn. root on urine volume

Group	Treatment	Dose	Volume of urine (mL/hr)
1	0.5% Sodium CMC (control)	-	1.45 \pm 0.13
2	Furosemide (Standard)	10mg/Kg	5.20 \pm 0.25*
3	Low dose	200mg/Kg	3.28 \pm 0.22
4	High dose	400mg/Kg	4.52 \pm 0.12*

Values given are mean \pm S.E.M of six observations. All the values are compared with control group and considered significant at * $p < 0.001$.

Figure 1: Effect of *Solanum indicum* Linn. root on urine volume

Diuretic index

Table 2: Effect of *Solanum indicum* Linn. root on diuretic index

Group	Treatment	Dose	Diuretic index
1	0.5% Sodium CMC (control)	-	-
2	Furosemide (Standard)	10mg/Kg	3.58
3	Low dose	200mg/Kg	2.26
4	High dose	400mg/Kg	3.12

The diuretic index values of test groups were 2.26 and 3.12, respectively indicating a good diuretic activity while maximum diuretic effect was observed at the dose of 400 mg/kg of extract (Table 2).

Lipschitz value

Table 3: Effect of *Solanum indicum* Linn. root on Lipschitz value

Group	Treatment	Dose	Lipschitz value
1	0.5% Sodium CMC (control)	-	-
2	Furosemide (Standard)	10mg/Kg	-
3	Low dose	200mg/Kg	0.63
4	High dose	400mg/Kg	0.87

The Lipschitz values showed that at the doses of 200 and 400 mg/Kg of ethanolic *Solanum indicum* L. root was having 63% and 87% of diuretic activity, respectively compared with furosemide (Table 3).

Estimation of urine electrolytes

Table 4: Effect of *Solanum indicum* Linn. root on urinary electrolyte excretion

Group	Treatment	Electrolyte concentration of urine (mMol/L)		
		Sodium	Potassium	Chloride
1	0.5% Sodium CMC (control)	109.4±12.07	35.4±21.24	78.3±34.29
2	Furosemide (Standard)	127.4±18.17*	68.7±28.46*	197.2±14.15*
3	Low dose	119.9±25.18*	39.5±13.14	114.9±36.28

4	High dose	131.8±11.30*	55.3±32.20*	187.2±25.47*
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Values given are mean ± S.E.M of six observations. All the values are compared with control group and considered significant at *p < 0.001.

Figure 2: Effect of Solanum indicum Linn. root on urinary sodium, potassium and chloride levels

Ethanollic root extract of *Solanum indicum* Linn. produces natriuretic effects in a dose dependent manner as shown in Figure 2. The concentration of sodium excreted in test group 4 i.e., high dose treatment was greater than that of reference standard showing that at higher doses, *Solanum indicum* Linn. has significant natriuretic effects.

The oral administration of ethanollic root extract of *Solanum indicum* Linn. also produced kaliuretic

effects in a dose-dependent manner (Figure 2). But here the excretion of potassium by the test groups is lower when compared to the standard.

The oral administration of ethanollic root extract of *Solanum indicum* Linn. increases the chloride excretion in a dose-dependent manner (Figure 2). But here the excretion of chloride by the test groups is lower when compared to the standard.

In vitro anti-urolithiatic activity by titrimetry method

Table 5: Percentage dissolution of calcium oxalate

Sl. no.	Group	Dissolved calcium oxalate (mg)	Percentage dissolution (%)
1	Blank	0	0
2	Ethanollic <i>Solanum indicum</i> L. root extract	0.566	56.6
3	Cystone (Standard)	0.624	62.4

Figure 3: Calcium oxalate dissolved with ethanollic Solanum indicum Linn. root extract and standard Cystone

From Table 5, The ethanolic extract of *Solanum indicum* Linn. root showed high (56.6%) percentage dissolution of calcium oxalate while Cystone showed higher percentage dissolution (65%) of calcium oxalate by the Titrimetric method.

DISCUSSION

The Ayurvedic medical system uses *Solanum indicum* Linn., also called "Brihati" in Sanskrit, either alone or in combination with other medications. The root of the plant is commonly used in the event of dysuria and incontinence. Diuretics are chemicals which accelerate the production of urine. Diuretics generally function by increasing the output of urine along with sodium excretion from the body through the urine. Diuretics such as the high-ceiling loop and thiazides diuretic have been associated with several side effects, such as electrolyte and metabolic changes, new-onset diabetes development, renin-angiotensin system activation and weakening of sexual function. This fact necessitates that there is a strong need for novel diuretics which are relatively safe with better or equivalent diuretic activity. Urolithiasis is the development of urinary calculi (stones), which can occur anywhere in the urinary system. One of the most prominent urinary tract illnesses that have affected humans is urolithiasis. Numerous herbal remedies have shown beneficial effects against urolithiasis, and these products have generally been proven to have fewer side effects and toxicity.

According to studies, the majority of herbs with anti-urolithiatic action have a strong diuretic effect. The ability of these herbs to increase urine rate and volume (diuresis), which promotes the elimination of small crystals and lowers the possibility of these crystals developing or aggregating, can be used to explain how diuresis contributes to the anti-urolithiatic property of these herbs. Diuretics have been developed and are commonly used as anti-urolithiatic medications. The preliminary phytochemical investigation revealed the presence of alkaloids, glycosides, flavonoids, tannins, phenolic compounds, and sterols in the ethanolic root extract of *Solanum indicum* Linn. Numerous chemicals, including flavonoids, saponins, and organic acids, have been shown in studies to be potentially responsible for the diuretic effects of

plants^[12]. According to studies, the diuretic properties of flavonoids may result from their interaction with adenosine A1 receptors^[13]. Some studies have also shown that diuretic activity might be due to the consequence of alkaloids^[14]. The exact site, molecule, and cellular mechanisms have not yet been fully understood.

Following the OECD-423 guidelines (Acute Toxic Class Method- Limit test), the acute toxicity assessments of the ethanolic root extract were carried out. No mortality or acute toxicity was seen up to 2000mg/kg of body weight. An acute toxicity investigation found that the ethanolic extract of *Solanum indicum* L. was comparatively nontoxic up to 2000 mg/kg of body weight, indirectly indicating the extract's safety profile. Therefore, the fraction's LD50 was higher than 2000 mg/kg body weight. Although the limit test results might not be precise, this type of testing is usually sufficient to identify the range of dose(s) at which the tested substance's LD50 is placed.^[15]

The results we obtained show that ethanolic root extract of *Solanum indicum* Linn. increased urine excretion in a dose-dependent manner, with greatest diuretic effects being seen at a dose of 400 mg/kg. Good diuretic activity is interpreted as values of the diuretic index greater than 1.50, moderate diuretic activity as values between 1.00 and 1.50, light diuretic activity as values between 0.72 and 1.00, and no diuretic activity as values below 0.72. The treated groups' diuretic index values were 2.26 and 3.12, respectively, showing that crude extract has extremely strong diuretic activity, particularly at a dose of 400 mg/kg. In accordance with Lipschitz values, the plant had 63% and 87% diuretic effectiveness when compared to furosemide at the low dose and high dose of crude extract respectively. The increase in diuresis induced by the ethanolic root extract of *Solanum indicum* Linn. was reflected in similar manners in urinary ionic excretion. It significantly increased excretion of urinary electrolytes (Na⁺, K⁺ and Cl⁻) in a dose dependent manner. Sodium is regarded as a significant external component in primary hypertension. Increased sodium intake has been found in numerous studies that it increases arterial blood pressure^[16]. Ethanolic *Solanum indicum* L. root extract treatment increased urine sodium excretion in

the experimental rats, indicating that plant could have potential as an antihypertensive medication. It's interesting to note that when compared to furosemide, ethanolic root extract of *Solanum indicum L.* showed an increased natriuretic impact at a dose of 400 mg/kg.

The excretion of potassium in the urine was also significantly increased in a dose-dependent pattern. It is appealing that the excretion of potassium in the treated groups was lower than that of the reference standard group, indicating that the ethanolic root extract of *Solanum indicum L.* has potassium-sparing capabilities when compared to that of the standard furosemide. Also, the chloride excretion was also increased in a dose dependent manner but lower than that of the standard furosemide. These findings lead to the suggestion that ethanolic root extract's diuretic effect may be due to the inhibition of aldosterone action or epithelial sodium channels. To test this hypothesis, however, additional study is needed.

The percentage inhibition of calcium oxalate crystallization of the ethanolic root extract was calculated by using formula. The present study clearly indicates the ethanolic root extract of *Solanum indicum Linn.* showed higher calcium oxalate crystallization inhibition (56.6 %) for the titrimetric method. While Cystone, a prescribed medicine for renal calculi showed highest inhibition (62.4%) in terms of formation of calcium oxalate precipitation.

CONCLUSION

The results of the present study demonstrated that the oral treatment of ethanolic root extract of *Solanum indicum Linn.* on animals showed prominent diuretic activity. The ethanolic root extract at 200 and 400 mg/kg body weight showed dose dependent rise in diuretic activity. These findings lead to the suggestion that ethanolic root extract's diuretic effect may be due to the inhibition of aldosterone action or epithelial sodium channels. The in vitro study of the ethanolic root extract showed potent anti urolithiatic activity. Since there isn't a synthetic medication that adequately treats urolithiasis at the moment, this study confirms the anti-urolithiatic action of ethanolic root extract of *Solanum indicum Linn.* for further development.

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